

GENDER CHARACTERISTICS OF SCHOOL ACTIVITY REGULATION OF GRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article presents an analysis of the problem of gender differences in the motivation of educational activities of students of the graduating class. Methodology of psychological and pedagogical research aimed at determining the gender and age characteristics of the manifestation of students' knowledge interests and responding to these characteristics of the educational content is described. Also, the gender characteristics of the systematization of students' educational activities are highlighted.

Key words: educational system, gender approach, systematization, individual work process, scientific activity, personality problems.

Introduction:

Improvement of the education system, introduction of new educational standards based on the competence-based approach, which defines a new level of social and cultural preparation of boys and girls for later life, is related to the qualitative improvement of the education level of schoolchildren. Determined the search for new technologies of education. It is necessary to look for methods that allow to mechanism the knowledge capacity of the students of the graduating class, to increase the level of motivation for educational activities. Therefore, it seems interesting and relevant for us to consider the gender approach to graduate education, taking into account the psychological characteristics of the student's gender. Today, the entire system of education is structured in such a way that school teachers unwittingly direct boys to technical subjects and girls to humanities. Studies conducted in schools in different countries have shown that boys are given, on average, more attention and time than girls, boys are more likely to demonstrate different experiences in the classroom, and girls are more likely to write minutes are more involved, teachers expect higher results from boys, especially in areas where abstract thinking is required, and value their work more highly. Boys get more attention, rewards, more informal communication. Thus, we show that the imperfection of the teacher's gender competence is expressed by the increase of social prejudices, gender discrimination, the violation of social interaction and hinders the comprehensive realization of the personality of both students and teachers.

The study of the psychological, social, and motivational characteristics of the gender role of the students of the graduating class, to pay more attention to the study of the differences and similarities in the social behavior of boys and girls, the characteristics, stereotypes, and roles that are considered characteristic of them. will help. I. F. Bogdanovich was one of the first to focus on the problem of specific characteristics of education of social and cultural competence of students of the graduating class, depending on their gender¹. They paid special

¹ Bogdanovich I.F. Letter to the publisher from the author of the book "On the Education of Youth" / I.F. Bogdanovich // Russian Bulletin. – 1808. – No. 9.

attention to the issue of educating girls, where they especially paid attention to the issue of the importance of social, cultural, spiritual education and moral qualities.

Based on the results obtained during psychological and pedagogical research, we developed practical recommendations based on the effective implementation of the gender approach in teaching for gymnasium management, which can be used in other educational institutions. The recommendations have four main directions: for the management of the educational institution, for teachers and specialists of the educational institution, for parents and students. Recommendations for the management of the educational institution are characterized by the organization of a pedagogical community aimed at implementing the gender principle of education as effectively as possible: increasing extracurricular zones for children's self-realization (sports, free time, daily activities skills, creativity, communication), organizing the experience of equal cooperation of boys and girls in joint activities (implementation of scientific and social projects, volunteering, creativity), traditional cultural stereotypes of the manifestation of emotional reactions withdrawal (encouraging boys to express their feelings, to reflect, for girls to develop mood self-regulation skills), to create conditions for reducing the level of anxiety in adulthood, games, conducting a parent training program that includes dramatization, exchange of roles, separate physical education classes, lectures, conversations, training, elements of Art therapy, etc.

For gymnasium teachers, we recommend the following:

- development of speech skills taking into account gender characteristics (development of fine motor skills in boys, encouragement of large, oral conversations in girls, development of written speech skills);
- when explaining new material, it is necessary to take into account the psycho-physiological characteristics of knowledge perception and acquisition by children of different genders (boys, a problematic situation before they act);
- active use of multimedia educational forms and methods to increase interest in learning among teenage children;
- In encouraging and punishing, it is necessary to strictly consider the gender characteristics of the perception and experience of success and failure, as well as to exclude forms of social criticism.

Recommendations for parents of students include the following areas of activity:

- establishing positive communication and positive interaction with the teachers of the educational institution for effective achievement of educational and educational goals and personal development of the child;
- mastering the ways and means of encouraging the child to learn and forming his positive educational motivation;
- use of gender approach principles in family education;
- establishing reliable and sensitive relations with the adult child in family education;
- regular and systematic interactions with the child in all spheres of activity: sports, hobbies, creativity, free time, education;
- mastery of school subjects to encourage the child to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities to improve quality academic performance and level.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the problem of the mental characteristics of men and women begins to be actively discussed: in the pages of periodicals, in pedagogical literature, at conferences on social and family education. The issue of teaching boys and girls together at school was reflected. The opinion of the public and the teachers on this matter was divided. Proponents of co-educating children of different genders believed that this would actually solve the problem of equality between men and women. K. D. Ushinsky studied the problem of a differentiated approach to raising children and emphasized that in order to achieve a better result in the teaching process, it is necessary to take into account the psychological characteristics of children of both genders². Taking into account the gender characteristics of the students of the graduating class, famous teachers considered the task of educating masculinity and femininity in the young generation as one of the most important tasks of moral formation of the individual.

In order to study the current state of the problem of taking gender characteristics into account in the education of adolescents, we studied the gender and age characteristics of the manifestation of students' knowledge interests and studied the educational content corresponding to these characteristics and conducted pedagogical research. The knowledge of human development as a representative of the child's gender does not fully satisfy the teachers' interest. Teachers do not always know how to organize, structure and regulate the educational process, including pedagogical situations related to the education of children according to gender, but they pay positive attention to the process of teaching schoolchildren based on the gender approach.

Our research showed that during the educational process, girls pay more attention to academic achievements, high grades, as a result, they develop a high sensitivity to the attitudes and expectations of other people, especially the opinions of teachers and parents. Social adaptability directs girls to adapt to a model of behavior that is directly or indirectly encouraged by the teacher. The behavior of boys is significantly different from that of girls at this age. As a rule, students of the graduating class immediately try to demonstrate their personal skills, knowledge, and achievements. If classroom activities are not interesting to them due to their ease or, on the contrary, difficulties, boys often start to break discipline, distract.

When studying the attitude of parents to the issue of raising children's social and cultural competence based on a gender approach, and the level of competence in this regard, we obtained the following results: according to parents, the role of the family in raising male/female qualities in a child is the difference between male and female. is an example of a relationship. In this case, the child is focused on imitating the parents of their gender. Parents strive to increase their children's psychological and pedagogical competence in gender motivation, teaching and upbringing. Parents who make a personal contribution to the upbringing of worthy men/women as full members of society, conduct educational conversations with children, set a personal example and work together.

The role of the mother in educating the social and cultural competence of the students of the graduating class is an example of the formation of femininity, moral education and

² Ushinsky K.D. Russian school / K.D. Ushinsky; comp. IN. Gusakova, ed. O.A. Platonov. – M.: Institute of Russian Civilization, 2015. – 688 p.

trusting relationships for the girl. The father's role is to set an example for the son in education, to nurture masculinity, and to set the future husband's standard for the daughter.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be noted that the knowledge about gender characteristics in the development of social and cultural competence in students of the graduating class depends on the objectivity of the educational process of teachers and parents objectively available teaching by understanding differences, should help develop the ability to organize it in such a way.

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